

Solution studies on ternary complex formation of bivalent metal ions with cephalaxine and amino acids, β -alanine and cysteine

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Studies on ternary complexes of Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Co^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} , with cephalaxine (HCEX) and some amino acids, viz. β -alanine (β -Ala) and cysteine (Cys), in the ratio 1 : 1 : 1, have been investigated by potentiometric technique at $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaClO_4) and temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in aqueous medium. The stability constants and S_{min} values of the ternary systems $\text{M}(\text{II})$ - β -Ala-HCEX (A) and $\text{M}(\text{II})$ -Cys-HCEX (B) have been calculated. The results have been discussed in terms of different statistical factors such as metal-ligand interaction, structure of the ligands and intramolecular ligand-ligand interactions.

Cephalaxine (HCEX) exhibits a broad-spectrum antibacterial activity, which is related to its ability to form complexes with metal ions¹.

The present study describes the results of an equilibrium study on the complex formation of Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Co^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} , hereafter $\text{M}(\text{II})$, with HCEX, in the presence of β -Ala and Cys, by potentiometric method at a fixed ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaClO_4) and temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$, in aqueous medium.

Results and discussion

Cephalaxine, HCEX has two ionisable hydrogen ions. Using the method of Irving and Rossotti², the pK_a values have been found to be $\text{pK}_{a1} = 2.65$ and $\text{pK}_{a2} = 9.75$. Mode of co-ordination of HCEX with $\text{M}(\text{II})$ is a function of side chain and also of pH ³. In the present study it has been found complexation of HCEX with $\text{M}(\text{II})$ is maximum after $\text{pH} \sim 7$ and hence the coordination in HCEX is taking place from the side chain amino group and carbonyl group³. HCEX acts as secondary ligand as the stability constants, of binary complexes it forms with $\text{M}(\text{II})$, are less than that of β -Ala or Cys complexes (Table 1). \bar{n} and pL values of the ternary complexes have been determined by using the equation suggested by Irving-Rossotti². The formation of ternary com-

plexes was confirmed from the shape of pH titration curves, i.e., there is lowering of potentiometric titration curves, representing the mixed system in comparison to the curve for binary complex of the metal with the secondary ligand⁴.

The stability constants of ternary complexes formed are found to be higher than the stability constants of either of the binary complexes (Table 1). The order of stability constants of the ternary systems has been found to be : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Pb}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mg}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$. This order is in good agreement with the order of Irving-Williams⁵.

In M - β -Ala-HCEX system, β -Ala forms six-membered chelate ring whereas HCEX forms five-membered chelate ring. Formation of one five-membered and one six-membered chelate ring in ternary system brings in more of ligand field symmetry and results in extra stabilization of the ternary system⁶.

Cysteine can act as bidentate ligand via (S, N) or (S, O) donor sites or as tridentate ligand via (S, N, O) sites in which S can form both σ and π bonds with metal ions during complexation. Thus M -S $d\pi$ - $d\pi$ interaction increases the stability of ternary complexes^{7,8}.

In all the ternary systems the complexation was observed to be maximum in the pH range ($\text{pH} 7$ – 9) to the extent of 50–75% except in the case of Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} where it is less than 40%. In none of the systems studied, hydrolysis was observed.

Experimental

pH -metric titrations were carried out with a PHM 83

Table 1. Formation constants and S_{\min} values of ternary M(II)-L₂-HCEX complexes of bivalent metal ions with L₂ = β -Ala and Cys in aqueous solution $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$

(i) 1 : 1 M(II)-ligand binary constants :

M(II)	HCEX		β -Ala		Cys	
	$\log K_{M(\text{HCEX})}^M$	S_{\min}	$\log K_{M(\beta\text{-Ala})}^M$	S_{\min}	$\log K_{M(\text{Cys})}^M$	S_{\min}
Cu ^{II}	7.51	0.1650	7.76	0.0002	7.60	0.0006
Pb ^{II}	7.12	0.0001	7.66	0.0052	7.34	0.0120
Ni ^{II}	6.93	0.0269	6.66	0.0036	6.98	0.0005
Zn ^{II}	6.31	0.0629	6.51	0.2250	6.64	0.0004
Co ^{II}	5.64	0.1657	6.41	0.2264	6.32	0.0005
Cd ^{II}	5.51	0.0042	5.74	0.0054	5.81	0.1125
Mn ^{II}	5.41	0.0007	5.68	0.1105	5.62	0.0045
Mg ^{II}	5.13	0.0074	5.24	0.0006	5.28	0.0035
Ca ^{II}	4.32	0.0358	4.84	0.0045	4.52	0.0025

(ii) 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 M(II)-L₂-HCEX ternary constants :

M(II)	β -Ala		Cys	
	$\log K_{M(\beta\text{-Ala})(\text{HCEX})}^M$	S_{\min}	$\log K_{M(\text{Cys})(\text{HCEX})}^M$	S_{\min}
Cu ^{II}	8.27	0.0054	10.24	0.0030
Pb ^{II}	8.12	0.0292	9.12	0.0055
Ni ^{II}	8.09	0.0095	8.25	0.0005
Zn ^{II}	7.56	0.0007	8.22	0.1358
Co ^{II}	6.97	0.0001	7.41	0.0299
Cd ^{II}	6.85	0.0062	6.48	0.0044
Mn ^{II}	6.75	0.0011	6.21	0.0060
Mg ^{II}	6.72	0.0003	5.13	0.0009
Ca ^{II}	6.13	0.0001	4.81	0.0021

Autocal pH-meter (Radiometer Copenhagen) with combined glass and calomel electrodes assembly. Cephalaxine (HCEX, Sigma), β -alanine (β -Ala) and cysteine (Cys) (A.R.) were used and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. All the metal ion solutions were prepared from A.R. samples of the corresponding sulphates or nitrates and standardized complexometrically⁹. Tetramethylammonium hydroxide, TMAH (E. Merck) (CH₃)₄NOH solution in double-distilled water was used as the titrant. It was standardized with a standard solution of oxalic acid. Perchloric acid (HClO₄) was standardized with standard TMAH solution. To ensure constant ionic strength during the titration an inert electrolyte sodium perchlorate, NaClO₄ (Riedel) was added in concentration greater than that of the complexing constituents.

pH-metric titration procedure : Determination of the formation constants of ternary complexes involved pH-metric titrations of a series of solutions of 2.0 ml (0.002 M) of the ligands containing 2.5 ml (0.05 M) of free HClO₄ in the

absence and in the presence of 0.2 ml (0.02 M) of the metal ions with a standard 0.05 M solution of TMAH. Formation constants were calculated by weighted least squares method¹⁰ of Sullivan *et al.*¹⁰. The titrations have been carried out in a covered double walled glass cell in the nitrogen atmosphere (i.e., O₂ free atmosphere, which ensures the absence of any side reaction), which was pre-saturated with double-distilled water. All measurements were made in aqueous medium at temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$, which was kept constant by using a Julabo F20 (West Germany) thermostat and at an ionic strength = 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

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